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The relationship between marketing communication activities and customer loyalty: Case of furniture product

Quang Van Ngo ^{1,*} and Luan Ngoc Trinh ²

¹ Faculty of Business Management, Hanoi University of Industry, Vietnam.

² Faculty of Business Administration, East Asia University of Technology, Vietnam.

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Abstract

Improving marketing communication activities plays an important role in improving customer loyalty. The study has provided theoretical foundations related to the research problem, thereby serving as a basis for building a model for the topic. The study selected the scope in Hanoi area, applying qualitative and quantitative research methods to evaluate the relationship between Marketing communication and customer loyalty. The author built a survey to obtain 219 questionnaires that met the research standards, using SPSS 22 software to process data. The research results show that there are 5 factors affecting loyalty including: brand presence, brand empathy, customer satisfaction, customer trust, brand reputation. trademark. The thesis has proposed a number of recommendations for businesses to improve communication activities,

Keyword: Customer loyalty; Customer trust; Communication activities; Marketing communication activities; Furniture product

1. Introduction

Loyalty plays a decisive role in creating direct profits of enterprises and long-term development, especially for businesses that develop and change business forms. Especially for a real estate-related business like Flexfit, which continuously works with many corporate customers, the importance of loyalty is at a new level, customers contribute a lot to the growth. strengthen the company's reputation. In order to retain customers, communication activities are indispensable, because communication about the business helps to generalize the image of the business in the hearts of customers and understand the business. However, during the internship period at Flexfit Joint Stock Company, the author found that the company's marketing communication activities still had many limitations such as: not really understand customers to give appropriate approach to each object causing misunderstanding that; customers know that Flexfit is a furniture company, not a connectivity platform; Using inappropriate communication tools leads to ineffective communication in the launch stage of the market... From the above analysis, the author decided to choose the topic: "Improving communication activities Marketing communication in order to improve customer loyalty for products of Flexfit Joint Stock Company" as the topic for the graduation thesis. not a connection platform; Using inappropriate communication tools leads to ineffective communication in the launch stage of the market... From the above analysis, the author decided to choose the topic: "Improving communication activities Marketing communication in order to improve customer loyalty for products of Flexfit Joint Stock Company" as the topic for the graduation thesis. not a connection platform; Using inappropriate communication tools leads to ineffective communication in the launch stage of the market... From the above analysis, the author decided to choose the topic: "Improving communication activities Marketing communication in order to improve customer loyalty for products of Flexfit Joint Stock Company" as the topic for the graduation thesis.

*Corresponding author: Quang Van Ngo

1.1. Basis on communications and loyalty

1.1.1. . Marketing communication

Concept of communication

Communication is the process of conveying information, orientation and sharing for the purpose of persuading a person or a group of people, a certain community of people to support, agree, or follow. In the present time, communication has developed in the direction of multimedia communication, which means that the content conveyed to the public is no longer the traditional method of "listening, reading, viewing", when viewing a piece of information, consumers can receive a variety of forms such as audio, video clips, pictures... For example, when reading newspapers, consumers sometimes do not have to spend time holding the newspaper, but instead where students can work while reading newspapers through the form of "listening to newspapers".

Marketing Communication is a form of communication that uses advertising channels, public relations... to convey messages to customers to increase customers' awareness and loyalty to products or services.

The role of marketing communication:

Marketing communication has a great influence on issues in today's society, affecting public perception. It can be said that, with invisible power, the media can pull the public to the story they draw, even if it is not true. The behavior is repeated many times and gradually becomes a habit, a routine, and gradually forms what is called a social norm. It is also thanks to the media that these issues are gradually accepted by society, spread quickly and positively to other publics. Some typical subjects affected by the media: for government units, the state; for the public group; For economy;

1.1.2. . Customer loyalty

The concept of customer loyalty

Customer loyalty is the willingness and will of a customer to continually use and create support for a brand or product. Loyal customers tend to appreciate a brand, have a high satisfaction index, and will often repurchase or continue using that brand's products instead of switching to another brand.

Customer loyalty describes the relationship between the brand and the customer, the product's interaction with the user, the level of readiness to interact, the willingness to buy, the willingness to buy again and again. Customer loyalty helps brands grow, of great importance, this is what companies strive to build.

1.2. Research models and hypothesis

Figure 1 Proposed research model

- Hypothesis H1: Brand presence has a positive effect on customer loyalty
- Hypothesis H2: Brand reputation has a positive effect on brand loyalty.
- Hypothesis H3: Brand empathy has a positive effect on loyalty
- Hypothesis H4: Customer satisfaction has a positive effect on customer loyalty
- Hypothesis H5: Customer trust positively affects customer loyalty

2. Material and methods

Secondary data collection source: The author conducts research and synthesizes brand-related documents through social media sources, statistics from researchers in the furniture industry such as DongSuh, Innovativehub... At the same time, the author collects secondary data related to business and communication activities (Fanpage and Website) of Flexfit Joint Stock Company.

Primary data collection source: The author conducts quantitative research, in the form of a survey of partners and customers of Flexfit Joint Stock Company. Through the survey to understand the effectiveness of the Company's communication activities, thereby providing the basis for proposing solutions that are most suitable to the current situation of the company.

Primary data was collected through the official questionnaire, in the group questionnaire using 5 independent variables. Then, the minimum sample size is $n = 50 + 5.29 = 195$. The group collected 219 suitable questionnaires and then entered and processed the data.

After receiving the answers, we coded and entered the data, then analyzed it using SPSS software version 22. The scales in this study were tested through the Cronbach Alpha reliability assessment and the Cronbach Alpha method. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA). Finally, multivariate regression analysis was performed to test the hypothesis of the study.

3. Results and discussion

After receiving the answers, we coded and entered the data, then analyzed it using SPSS software version 22. The scales in this study were tested through the Cronbach Alpha reliability assessment and the Cronbach Alpha method. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA). Finally, multivariate regression analysis was performed to test the hypothesis of the study.

3.1. Analysis of sample characteristics

Table 1 Demographic information of survey respondents

Factor	Ingredient	Quantity	Ratio (%)
Sex	Male	163	74.87%
	Female	56	25.57%
Year old	From 18 to 30	26	11.87%
	From 30 to 45	115	52.51%
	From 45 to 60	78	35.62%

Regarding gender: The number of survey participants is male, accounting for 74.87% (163 people). Meanwhile, the number of female interviewers accounted for 25.57% (equivalent to 56 people).

About age: Out of a total of 219 respondents to the survey, there are 26 people aged from 18 to 30 years old, accounting for 11.87%, 115 people aged from 30 to 45 years old, accounting for 52.51%, 78 people aged from 45 to 60 years old, accounting for 35.62%. From this result, it can be seen that the company's customers are mostly between the ages of 30 and 45. This is the ideal age for the target customer segment of the business.

3.2. Statistical analysis mean

It can be seen from the observed variables of the 5 independent variables that all have values that clearly show the degree of close agreement with the survey subjects. The standard deviation has a small fluctuation, showing that the survey object has many similarities with the variable.

3.3. Testing the reliability of the scale

The test results show that the overall Cronbach - Alpha coefficient is high from 0.7 to nearly 1, clearly showing that the observed variables have a good correlation with the overall scale of the scale. The survey scale ensures high reliability with the Cronbach - Alpha coefficients having values above 0.6. In addition, the correlation coefficient of the total variables is greater than 0.3 (Zikmund 2010), showing that the variables in the scale are quite linked together and are good measure variables. No variables were removed from the scale and the scale was suitable for further EFA analysis.

3.4. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA)

Table 2 KMO coefficient and Bartlett's test for independent factors

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.855
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2600.194
	Df.	231
	Sig.	0.000

Bartlett's test shows that the coefficient KMO = 0.855 > 0.5, Sig = 0.00, shows that the hypothesis of the overall correlation matrix is that the identity matrix is rejected, that is, the variables are correlated with each other and satisfy the condition. conditions in factor analysis, the data is suitable for analysis.

Multilinear regression analysis: The results show that R² adjusted by 0.674 shows that the independent variable included in the regression affects 67.4 % of the change of the dependent variable, the remaining 32.6% is due to variables outside the model and random error. Durbin - Watson coefficient is used to test the correlation of adjacent errors with values ranging from 1 to 4 and the more the Durbin - Watson coefficient approaches 0, the error parts are positively correlated. Durbin - Watson coefficient = 1.985 is in the range from 1.5 to 2.5, so no first order series autocorrelation occurs.

3.5. Testing the hypothesis

Sig.F coefficient (ANOVA table) = 0.000, we see that the included variables are statistically significant at the 5% level of significance. Thus, the independent variables in the model are related to the dependent variable.

Table 3 Regression analysis

Coefficients								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		Beta	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
fFirst	(Constant)	-2.130	0.274		-7,784	0.000		
	B1	0.459	0.052	0.405	8,781	0.000	0.702	1.425
	B2	0.100	0.048	0.084	2,092	0.000	0.929	1.076
	B3	0.344	0.056	0.278	6.163	0.000	0.735	1,360
	B4	0.316	0.064	0.220	4,946	0.000	0.756	1.323
	B5	0.247	0.062	0.173	4.014	0.000	0.801	1.248

(Source: Author's calculation on SPSS 22 software)

With the sample size of 219 observed variables, the significance level α was chosen to be 0.05. Performance analysis shows:

The independent variables in the model fit perfectly because the Sig coefficient < 0.05 (Coefficients Table)

The VIF coefficients of the independent variables in the model are all less than 5, so the phenomenon of multicollinearity among the independent variables in the model does not have a significant effect on the regression model.

The normalized regression model is written as follows:

$$Y = 0.405*B1 + 0.084*B2 + 0.278*B3 + 0.22*B4 + 0.173*B5$$

In there:

- Y: Value of dependent variable "Customer loyalty"
- B1: Value of the independent variable "Brand presence"
- B2: Value of the independent variable "Brand reputation"
- B3: Value of the independent variable "Brand empathy"
- B4: Value of independent variable "Customer satisfaction"
- B5: Value of the independent variable "Customer trust"

The research results show that variables: brand presence, brand reputation, brand empathy, customer satisfaction, customer trust directly affect customer loyalty. The original research hypotheses given by the author are all suitable and statistically significant when using the study.

3.6. Solutions and recommendations

3.6.1. Solution (there are 4 solutions)

First, increase interaction with consumers and increase consumer awareness of the company's presence.

- Develop short video content
- Increase posting frequency on platforms
- Promote Offline Marketing communication activities
- Create high-quality content
- Organizing events, exhibitions, fairs
- Search engine optimization

Second, building a brand that meets the social and psychological needs of consumers creates their emotional impact.

- Create emotional content that raises a sense of national identity
- Organize and participate in volunteering and charity campaigns

Third, do market research and conduct product promotion based on customer preferences – useful for bringing close value to customers. To research the market and conduct product promotion in the furniture industry, you can take the following steps:

- Understanding customer needs and preferences
- Get to know your competitors
- Create unique and attractive products
- Conduct product promotion
- Measure the effectiveness of promotional activities

Fourth, improve the quality of promotional content – give customers a real experience before using the product. In order for customers to have a pre-purchase experience, the furniture industry group can apply the following methods:

- Create a model of the interior of the store
- Using 3D . technology
- Free consulting service
- Provide product samples for free

4. Conclusion

In summary, the study has synthesized theories and related documents to propose a research model including 5 independent variables affecting brand loyalty. The study also applies to furniture products. Research shows that brand presence has the strongest impact on brand loyalty. Through the analysis results, the research shows that businesses need to strengthen communication solutions to improve brand preference in the minds of target customers. Research also confirms the important role of building and implementing communication programs to build brand empathy as well as customer satisfaction. Through this, businesses can increase customer loyalty. The study also has some limitations to serve as a basis for future research. Specifically, the new study examines the direct impact of independent variables on the dependent variable, without mediating or moderating variables. This makes it possible for the study to miss some important factors.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors proclaim no conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study

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